

Living next to Soren Kierkegaard
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Søren Kierkegaard and I did not use to be friends. Actually, we did not get along at all before my 40th birthday. Now we have become best neighbors.

Growing up in the world's most secular society, Denmark, Christianity and spirituality was not an essential part of my upbringing. Nor was philosophy. I was not familiar with Danish philosopher and theologian Kierkegaard's writings in my childhood or my youth. I heard his name. Nothing else.

This is not unusual. Contrary to what most foreigners think, Kierkegaard is not very famous in Denmark. Most Danish people are not familiar with the writings of Kierkegaard. Actually, Kierkegaard is not a particularly Danish writer. His thoughts do not reflect Danish culture and mentality. Or else, it is more correct to say that Kierkegaard's writings form a contrast to common Danish norms, values and ways of thinking. Kierkegaard sets the individual the task of breaking free from conventional living in order to become itself as oneself and meet God. According to Kierkegaard, this is fundamentally a spiritual task, but Kierkegaard also uses the new science of psychology to help him explore the anxiety and despair of the individual when faced with the fundamental challenge of discovering and choosing itself.

Being the child of a doctor and a nurse, born in 1972, my personal ambition as a young man was to become a psychiatrist. However, when I started working in a psychiatric hospital, I did not feel that medicine and the hospital sector was able to contain humanity and humanistic ideas. Instead, I went on to do a BA and a Master's degree in Philosophy and History of Ideas at Aarhus University as well as a Master's degree in Humanities and Health Studies. While the Philosophy Department at that time did not have any teaching or research in Kierkegaard's writings, they were rather popular at the Department of the History of Ideas, specializing in intellectual history and Continental philosophy. However, even though I choose to do my major in the history of ideas, I never caught an interest in Kierkegaard. On the contrary, I felt some dislike and even discomfort at his Christian and spiritual tone, and I did not read more than a single page of Kierkegaard's writings before rejecting them all together.

After completing my two master's degrees, I felt an urge to engage in something more practical than philosophy and I spent the following 9-10 years establishing a counselling unit at Aarhus University for students with lasting mental disorders. Alongside, I studied psychology at Aalborg University, and I did a foundation course in Psychotherapy and Counselling at Regent's University London. The approach of existential therapy spoke to me, and I began to study at the New School of Psychotherapy and Counselling, which gave me a chance to become more familiar with Kierkegaard's psychological thoughts.

When I was 30 years old, a spiritual person told me that a major change would happen to me at the age of 40. Because I did not believe in spiritual or religious insights, I purely rejected this statement. However, two weeks after my 40th birthday, I decided to make the greatest choice in my life so far. I felt it necessary to leave my position as head of counselling and teaching associate professor, without having any new opportunities in sight. Suddenly, Kierkegaard's were very relevant to my. More than anything else, I had ever read. In his groundbreaking work, *The Concept of Anxiety* (1844/2009), Kierkegaard was writing exactly about what I was going through. No other philosophers, psychologists or psychotherapists were able to elucidate my experience

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on the same level. Kierkegaard's book portrayed the feeling, immediately experienced by human beings during fundamental life changes or crisis. The feeling of existential anxiety, which I discovered was not at all just a theoretical concept or an abstract idea. The fundamental feeling of losing your ground, looking into the abyss of nothingness.

I got the feeling that I had to start my life all over. Not just concerning my job, but back to the rough ground all over. What was I supposed to do? I began visiting Kierkegaard's graveyard every morning at Assistens Cemetery, the burial site of a large number of Danish notables such as Kierkegaard and Hans Christian Andersen. The cemetery is the largest and most important greenspace in the Nørrebro district of Copenhagen, and it is only five minutes of walk from my home. Every morning, I asked Kierkegaard what I was supposed to do with my life. Then I went home, spending the rest of the day engaged in reading and writing texts on philosophy. Somehow, I just rediscovered my original interest in philosophy and started to dive into the thoughts of Kierkegaard as well as the thoughts of Friedrich Nietzsche, Lucius Annaeus Seneca, Epictetus, Marcus Aurelius and many others.

One morning, I stood in front of Kierkegaard's burial site, asking the same question once more. Suddenly, I realized that Kierkegaard has already given me the answer to my prayers. The answer to my question was that I went to ask him every morning. In other words. My questioning and my search for answers was the answer to prayers. Who was I? Who was I supposed to be? Where was I going? In the midst of anxiety, I had discovered and chosen myself as a person, fundamentally engaged in searching for wisdom. The original meaning of the Greek word *philosophia* (φιλοσοφία) is the pursuit of wisdom, involving that the philosopher is just a human being who is only able to love and search for wisdom but is never able to become as wise person, possessing wisdom. That was how ancient Greek philosopher Pythagoras coined the term.

What does it mean? When I realized, the meaning of my life was to engage in some kind of quest for wisdom, my life slowly began to heal. Kierkegaard and I did not use to be friends. Now Kierkegaard has become my favorite neighbor as well as my preferred spiritual guide. I did have the experience of some kind of spiritual awakening, allowing me to enter a different level of being and beginning to grasp the divine aspects of being. Finding inner peace and tranquility. Sometimes opening your eyes may be the most painful thing you ever have to do. However, what Kierkegaard gave to me, I now have the possibility of passing on by working with clients.

References

Kierkegaard, S. (2009). *Kierkegaard's Writings, I-XXVI*. Princeton: Princeton University Press